

GIUSEPPE BALSAMO AND FREEMASONRY FOR ENGLISH READERS: INDIRECT TRANSLATION AND IDEOLOGICAL REFRAMING AT THE END OF THE EIGHTEENTH CENTURY

Justyna Łukaszewicz

University of Wrocław (Poland)

Email: justyna.lukaszewicz@uwr.edu.pl

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19331030>

Keywords: indirect translation, peritexts, ideological manipulation, Enlightenment, Freemasonry

The study adopts a cultural-historical perspective, reading indirect translation as a site of ideological negotiation in the late Enlightenment.

Published anonymously in Rome in 1791, the booklet *Compendio della vita e delle gesta di Giuseppe Balsamo* presents a strongly polemical account of Cagliostro's life and a harsh condemnation of Freemasonry. Written by Giovanni Barberi, a senior papal official involved in Cagliostro's trial before the Holy Office, the text aimed to legitimize the proceedings and their outcome in the eyes of European public opinion. Its rapid dissemination through translations into several languages makes it a particularly revealing case for the study of indirect translation.

This paper examines the English translation *The Life of Joseph Balsamo* (1791), produced via a French relay version. By systematically comparing the English text with both the Italian source and the French intermediary—and by referring to the Polish indirect translation—the study investigates how ideological meanings are reshaped through relay translation.

Methodologically, the analysis focuses on peritextual elements (titles, prefaces, footnotes), understood, following Genette, as interpretative thresholds that frame the reception of the text. Particular attention is paid to the relationship between the English version and the French relay translation, the handling of footnotes, the positioning of the translator vis-à-vis the reader, and the strategies used to recalibrate the ideological tone of the edition.

The comparison reveals that ideological manipulation operates at every stage of transmission but takes different forms depending on the target culture. While the French version introduces explicitly pro-Masonic elements and the Polish edition reinforces the original papal and anti-Masonic stance, the English translation reframes the narrative through marked anti-papal accents.

Rather than a single two-arched bridge, the transmission of Barberi's pamphlet across Europe can be described as a multiple-arched bridge leading to various translations and editions strategically shaped for different European audiences.

References:

Primary Sources

1. [Barberi G.]. (1791). *Compendio della vita, e delle gesta di Giuseppe Balsamo denominato il conte Cagliostro che si è estratto dal processo contro di lui formato in Roma l'anno 1790 e che può servire di scorta per conoscere l'indole della setta de' Liberi Muratori*. Roma: Stamperia della Reverenda Camera Apostolica.
2. [Barberi G.]. (1791). *Vie de Joseph Balsamo connu sous le nom de Comte Cagliostro, extraite de la Procédure instruite contre lui à Rome, en 1790, traduite d'après l'original italien, imprimé à*

la Chambre Apostolique ; enrichie de Notes curieuses, et ornée de son portrait. Paris – Strasbourg : Onfroy libraire – Jean-George Treuttel libraire.

3. [G. Barberi]. (1791). *The Life of Joseph Balsamo, commonly called Count Cagliostro: containing the singular and uncommon adventures of that extraordinary personage from his birth till his imprisonment in the castle of St. Angelo. To which are added, the particulars of his trial before the inquisition, the history of his confessions concerning common and Egyptian masonry, and a variety of other interesting particulars. Translated from the Original Proceedings published at Rome by Order of the Apostolic Chamber. With an engraved portrait of Cagliostro.* Londyn: C. and G. Kearsley.

4. [Barberi G.]. (1793). *Zycie Jozefa Balsamo znanego pod imieniem hrabi Cagliostro, z procesu rzymskiego w r. 1790 przeciw mu prowadzonego wyjęte, wytłumaczone i notami objaśnione do wyrozumienia Sekt Masańskich.* Wilno: Drukarnia ks. Bazyliańów.

Secondary Sources

1. Assis Rosa, A., Pięta H., & Maia Bueno, R. (2017). Theoretical, methodological and terminological issues regarding indirect translation: An overview. *Translation Studies*, 10:2, 113-132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14781700.2017.1285247>

2. Batchelor, K. (2018). *Translation and Paratexts.* London: Routledge.

3. Catalano, G. & Marcialis, N. (eds) (2020). *InTRAlinea*, Special Issue: *La traduzione e i suoi paratesti* https://www.intraline.org/specials/traduzione_paratesti

4. Genette, G. (2002) [1987]. *Seuils.* Paris : Éditions du Seuil.

5. Ivaska L., Pięta H., & Gambier, Y. (2023). Past, present and future trends in (research on) indirect literary translation. *Perspectives*, Special Issue, 31(5), 775-786. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0907676X.2023.2221388>.

6. Łukaszewicz, J. (2018). Nietolerancja w polskim (1793) i francuskim (1791) przekładzie włoskiej książki o zagadkowym Józefie Balsamo i jego tajemniczej działalności (1791). In: M. Pawłowska & T. Wysłobocki (eds), *Dawne literatury romańskie w świecie tolerancji i nietolerancji, zagadek i tajemnic.* Kraków: Universitas, 147-155.

7. Łukaszewicz, J. (2019). Peritext in Polish Translations from Italian in the Eighteenth Century: Education or Manipulation? *Przekładaniec*, special issue: *Translation History in the Polish Context*, 28-45. <https://doi.org/10.4467/16891864ePC.19.002.11260>

8. Monti, E. & Schnyder, P. (eds) (2011). *Autour de la retraduction. Perspectives littéraires européennes.* Paris : Orizons.

9. Papadima, M. (2011). Głos tłumacza w peritekście jego przekładu: przedmowa, posłowie, przypisy i inne zwierzenia. *Między Oryginałem a Przekładem*, 17, 13-32.

10. Pellatt, V. (2013). Packaging the product: a case study of verbal and non-verbal paratext in Chinese-English translation. *The Journal of Specialised Translation*, Issue 20 – July, 86-106.

11. Quatriglio, G. (Ed.). (1995). *Giovanni Barberi, Compendio della vita e delle gesta di Giuseppe Balsamo denominato il conte Cagliostro.* Milano: Mursia.

12. Sardin, P. (2007). De la note du traducteur comme commentaire : entre texte, paratexte et prétexte, *Palimpsestes*, 20. <http://journals.openedition.org/palimpsestes/99>.